

Appendix II

Clustered elements, capturing all roles and the do/be/feel goals from the e-workshops

Roles	Do goals	Be goals	Feel goals
Average users	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have secret chats 2. Delete advertising messages 3. Edit stories 4. Block ads while playing games 5. Send large size documents 6. Play all kinds of games and Integrate all browser games 7. Restrict some people from seeing any information related to me 8. Want app to be as basic as possible 9. Turn Voice Messages into Texts 10. Select for how long people can see my stories 11. Scan and translate 12. Remove gaming feature 13. Filter ads for my needs only 14. Constrain others from deleting my messages 15. Delete others' messages 16. Pay via Facebook Messenger 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cryptographic; high-quality 2. Easy; Fast; Transparent; user-friendly 3. Ubiquitous 4. Automatic and configured 5. Fast; cross-functional 6. Optimized; benevolent, easy, fast 7. Secure, easy to do 8. easy to use and user-friendly 9. protected and intuitive 10. fast, and secure 11. fast, and flawless 12. Large-scale; Wide, Common, automatic, and safe 13. secure, filtered 14. well protected 15. Inconspicuous and fast 16. Secure and fast 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assured; Safe; strong 2. Empowered; Unpretentious; simple 3. Confident 4. forceful, involved, respectful, and conscious 5. unchained, and capable 6. engaged, imaginative, competitive, fictional and joyful; connected 7. free, safe, and unoccupied 8. calm, a little bit isolated 9. relieved of the burden; Loved; appreciated 10. appreciated, cherished, and valued 11. Assured; Optimistic; understood 12. more realistic, less or noncompetitive; present 13. Well-informed'; Relatable; free 14. to be accepted and appreciated 15. forceful and dominant, and free 16. tech-savvy, carefree, and unrestrained
Government representatives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Get all the detailed information about the person 2. Listen to all voice messages 3. Read all the messages from all chats 4. See all transactions 5. Restrict some games 6. See all messages/stories and etc., which have been edited 7. Block irrelevant or dangerous ads 8. Move messages from 3rd parties to spam folder 9. Listen to the voice calls 10. Restrict app for a specific person 11. Convert voice messages into text format 12. Impact people choices 13. Restrict advertisers from doing extensive targeting 14. Be in charge of all the chatbots or other automatic functions and Prevent all kinds of fraud 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. fast, cheap, and flawless 2. fast, and secure 3. seamless, fast, and secure 4. Intuitive and precise 5. Fast, easy to use, safe, automatic 6. fast, accessible 7. Automatic; Fast; Secure; transparent 8. cryptographic, and logical 9. Secure, invisible 10. Fast 11. cross-functional, fast, secure 12. seamless, and cryptographic 13. protective and encrypted 14. Proprietary, Protective, secure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assured; Safe; Strong; close up, and well-informed 2. in control; impetuous 3. well-informed, knowledgeable, empowered; controlling 4. dominant, in control, and undismayed 5. Assured; in control; powerful, secure, unattached 6. assured and secure; confident 7. impactful, dominant, and ruling; powerful, in charge, in control 8. self-indulgent, and protected 9. sure of myself, and prepotent 10. strong, and farsighted 11. dominant, smart, secure, protective, and backed up with data 12. supreme and authoritative 13. ruling and successful 14. in control, helpful, and powerful

<p>Advertisers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create a “circle” of customers to chat with 2. Cross-sell and up-sell 3. Listen to audio recordings 4. Send messages to all pages' followers 5. Impact people's choices 6. Create individual ads 7. Target non-brand-aware users. 8. Track people's data and behavior 9. Use the same ads for all users 10. Show ads to users during video calls 11. Host webinars, online events 12. Avoid ad blocking 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cross-functional; flexible 2. flawless,Intuitive, organized 3. Easy 4. Fast 5. Complete, without any errors, not noticeable 6. Secure, seamless, and very intuitive 7. manageable, usable and safe; in a single click 8. Secure, seamless, and very intuitive 9. cross-functional, and available in 1 click 10. Transparent; intuitive 11. Cross-functional and powerful 12. Safe; Fast; easy to implement; cross-functional 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. frugal; omnipresent; useful 2. Listened to 3. Comfortable; close to a client 4. Comfortable 5. Helpful; Assistive; caring 6. wholesome, communal and connected to my clients 7. Assured; Influential; fulfilled, Subservient; successful 8. free, careless, being sure 9. very individual and independent 10. presiding and omnipresent 11. heard, to be listened to, to get connected 12. powerful, self-governing, smart; successful, assured, free
---------------------------	---	--	---